

EFFECTS OF SINTERING CONDITIONS ON THE BOND STRENGTH OF ROLL BONDED METAL LAMINATE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Metal laminate composites of copper/aluminium were prepared by roll bonding at 430°C with a 60% rolling reduction. Post-rolling heat treatments were applied to the composite laminates to investigate the effect on the interface reaction between the bonded metals monitored. It was found that as the sintering temperature and duration increased, the interface of the metal laminates continued to grow to greater thickness. However growth of the interface did not always enhance the strength of the composites. Critical sintering conditions were found to exist for achieving the optimum bond strengths of the composites. It is evident that development of the optimum bond strength for the composites is related to the formation of the various intermetallic phases at the interface, determined by their energies of formation and the composition gradient across that interface. Development of the copper-rich porous structure, consisting of a Cu_9Al_4 phase, becomes dominant in the interface after sintering at high temperatures and/or prolonged periods. The porous structure is detrimental to the bonding of the metal laminates, leading to the observed low strengths. When aluminium-rich phases are developed during sintering at lower temperatures the bond strength of the laminate composites is increased.

KEYWORDS: metal laminate composites, sintering treatments, bond strength, intermetallic phases

INTRODUCTION

Advanced metal laminate composites have experienced rapid development in engineering applications in the past 30 years [1,2]. The composites usually possess high specific strengths, enhanced fatigue characteristics, improved wear performance and corrosion resistance, resulting in better service performance at reasonable manufacturing costs. Metal laminate composites can be manufactured by a number of methods and roll bonding is one of the major production methods commonly used in industry [3]. It is known that the bond strength and properties of the laminate composites are determined by several important processing parameters such as rolling temperature, deformation strain and sintering conditions. However the complex interface reaction of the metal laminates in the rolling and sintering processes which determine the bond strength of the composites are still not fully understood. In studying the formation of intermetallic phases at the interface of multilayer thin films, Jiang et al. [4] suggested that the interface reactions might be controlled by interfacial and grain boundary diffusion of the metallic elements in the area. Detail of the mechanism however has not been explored. The present paper reports results of a study of the effects of sintering conditions on the interface development and bond strength of the copper/aluminium laminate

composites. Examination of composition profile and formation of intermetallic phases across the interface of the metal laminates was performed. Relationship between the interface development and bond strength of the composites was studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Metal laminate composites of copper/aluminium were prepared by rolling, with a 60% reduction, at 430°C. Post-rolling heat treatments of the composites were employed at sintering temperatures from 350°C to 500°C for various periods to investigate the effect on interface reactions between the bonded metals. Bond strength of the composites was determined by peel tests conducted on samples of standard dimensions of 100 (L) x 10 (W) mm. Microstructure and interface morphology of the composites were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Composition profiles across the interface of the metal laminates were determined using energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) at 15 kV conducted in a scanning electron microscope. Thickness of the interface was determined as the distance between the 5%Cu/95%Al and 95%Cu/5%Al compositional boundaries in all the samples. Detection of the intermetallic phases at the interface of the laminate composites was carried out in a Siemens D5000 X-ray diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation at small scattering angles of $1^\circ - 3^\circ$.

RESULTS

The Effect of Sintering Time

A steady growth of the interface was evident in the specimens sintered at 450°C, as shown in the scanning electron micrographs of Figures 1a and 1b.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. Scanning Electron Micrographs showing Interface Development after Sintering at 450°C for (a) 1.5 hours (b) 3.0 hours

Figure 2 shows that as the sintering time increased, thickness of the copper/aluminium interface continuously increased from 5.7 μm in the as-rolled condition to 28.6 μm after the samples were sintered for a period of 3 hours.

Figure 2. Growth of the Interfacial Thickness at 450°C for Different Times

Figure 3 shows, however, that the bond strength of the composites had not shown similar trends with growth of the interface.

Figure 3 Variation of Peel Strength as a Function of Sintering Time at 450°C

As sintering time increased, the bond strength of the composites, measured by the peel test, increased from 59 N/cm in the as-rolled condition to a maximum of ~220 N/cm after a sintering of 1.5 hours and then substantially decreased to 83 N/cm after 3 hours as shown in

Figure 3, indicating the bonding of the metal laminates had been degraded after prolonged sintering. The results also reflect the complexity of the strength development of the composites and show no simple relationship between the interface growth and bond strength of the material.

The Effect of Sintering Temperature

The effect of sintering temperature on the bond strength of the laminates were investigated by heat treating the composites at temperatures from 350°C to 500°C for 0.5 and 2 hours. Figure 4 shows that as the sintering temperature increased, interface thickness increased for both conditions. After the samples were sintered for 0.5 hour, the interface of the metal laminates grew from a thickness of 8.2 μm at 350°C to 31.4 μm at 500°C. On the other hand, after sintered for 2 hours, thickness of the interface increased from 11.5 μm at 350°C to 33.8 μm at 500°C.

Figure 4. Interface Thickness as a Function of Sintering Temperature for Times of 0.5 and 2.0 Hours.

However an increase of the interface thickness did not always enhance the bond strength of the composites. After the samples were sintered for 0.5 hour, the peel strength of the samples increased from 192 N/cm at 350°C to a maximum of 216 N/cm at 400°C and decreased to a very low value of 17 N/cm at 500°C, Figure 5. In samples sintered for 2 hours, the peel strength increased from 141 N/cm at 350°C to a maximum of 186 N/cm at 400°C and then dropped to 10 N/cm at 500°C, Figure 5. The results indicated that the bonds of the metal laminates were significantly weakened after the composites were sintered at high temperatures.

Figure 5 Variation of Peel Strength with Temperature for Sintering Times of 0.5 and 2.0 Hours.

Fractography

Fracture surfaces of the tested samples were examined to identify origins of failure. Scanning electron microscopy of the fracture surface of the composites showed substantially different microstructural development under various sintering conditions. A porous structure consisting of many voids was generally observed in samples of lower peel strength after sintering at high temperatures and/or prolonged durations. A typical structure of the porous interface after sintering at 500°C for 2 hours is shown in Figure 6a. For the stronger laminates cleavage facets were usually dominant with features as those shown in Figure 6b. In general, the porous structure contained a copper content above 85% whereas the faceted structure consisted of less than 75% copper, resulting in formation of different phases and structures at the interface. X-ray diffraction measurement confirmed existence of different intermetallic phases in the samples. Cu_9Al_4 was found to be a dominant phase in the structures of high copper whilst formation of CuAl_2 was evident in those of lower copper content.

Figure 6 Scanning Electron Fractographs Showing the Structural Development after Sintering at (a) 500°C for 2 hours and (b) 400°C for 2 hours

DISCUSSION

Results of the present study show that a complex relationship exists between the interface development and bond strength of the composites in the sintering process. It was found that as the sintering temperature and/or duration increased, interface of the composites would continue to grow to greater thickness. However an increase of the interface thickness did not always enhance the strength of the composites. In general the peel strength of the composites initially rose to some maximum values and then dropped to low values after sintering at high temperatures for prolonged periods, indicating critical sintering conditions do exist for attaining optimum strengths of the composites. It is believed that development of the optimum strengths of the composites is related to the formation of various intermetallic phases at the interface area. Scanning electron microscopy on the fracture surface of the tested samples showed substantially different structures developed under various sintering conditions. A porous structure of higher copper content, as that shown in Figure 6a generally developed after sintering at a high temperature for a long period. Results of the peel tests showed that this porous structure was generally of low bond strength. X-ray diffraction measurement confirmed that Cu_9Al_4 was dominant in this structure. On the other hand, a cleavage facet structure was found to develop in the tested samples of high peel strength. The facet structure was usually of lower copper content with formation of CuAl_2 phase.

It is understood that both copper and aluminium atoms will be thermally activated in the sintering treatment. Moreover the diffusion rate of copper in aluminium is reported to be greater than that of aluminium in copper [5], thus creating a composition gradient of the metallic elements across the interface. Different intermetallic phases form across the interface of the composites. According to the phase equilibrium diagram of the copper-aluminium system [6], a copper-rich structure will then favour formation of Cu_9Al_4 - γ phase and as the copper content decreases, formation of CuAl_2 - θ phase will become possible. The EDS and X-ray diffraction measurements conducted in the present study confirmed the above phase development. It is recognised that with increasing sintering time, the volume of the copper-rich structure will increase because of the higher diffusion rate of copper atoms, thus increasing the volume of the porous structure. On the other hand, development of the Cu_9Al_4 and CuAl_2 phases will also be affected by their energies of formation. In a study of phase development of the copper-aluminium system, Jiang et al. [4] reported that the formation energies of Cu_9Al_4 and CuAl_2 are respectively 0.83 and 0.78 eV, showing that CuAl_2 may develop with lower activation energy. With a higher sintering temperature, the activation energy provided in the heating process is substantially increased, thus formation of Cu_9Al_4 becomes more viable at higher sintering temperatures. A comparison of the microstructures shown in Figures 6a and 6b shows a large difference in structure development between sintering at 400°C and 500°C, indicating the significant effect of sintering temperature on phase development at the interface. Development of a large volume of a porous structure at the interface will weaken the strength of the composites as reflected by the results obtained in the peel tests.

CONCLUSIONS

Interface development and bond strength of copper/aluminium metal laminate composites were examined in the present study. It was found that as the sintering temperature and duration increased, the interface of the metal laminates continued to become thicker. However, growth of the interface did not always enhance the strength of the composites. Critical sintering conditions for achieving optimum bond strengths of the composites were identified. It is believed that development of the optimum strengths of the composites is related to the formation of various intermetallic phases at the interface area that is in turn determined by the composition gradient across the interface of the composites and the formation energies of the various intermetallic phases. It is evident that development of the copper-rich porous structure of Cu_9Al_4 phase is detrimental to the bond strength of the laminates and formation of the aluminium-rich phases will enhance the strength of the composites as reflected by the results of the peel tests.

REFERENCES

1. Horvath, C. and Haynes, G., "Stainless Steel Claddings" *Automotive Engineering*, Vol. 99, 1991, pp.35-37.
2. Bittrich, J. and Fluegge, D., "Al-Cu Cladding Cables"., *Aluminium*, Vol. 21, 1984, pp.379-383.
3. Baboian, R. and Haynes, G., "Corrosion of Clad Metals" *ASM Metals Handbook*, Vol. 6, 1993, pp.887-890.
4. Jiang, H.G., Dai, J.Y., Tong, H.Y., Ding, B.Z., Song, Q.H. and Hu, Z.Q., "Interfacial Reactions on Annealing Cu/Al Multilayer Thin Films", *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol. 74, 1993, pp.6165-6169.
5. Askill, J., *Tracer Diffusion Data for Metals, Alloys and Simple Oxides*, IFI Plenum, New York, 1970, p.31.
6. Lu, J.Q. and Yi, W.Z., *Metallurgical Equilibrium Diagrams of Binary Alloys*, Science and Technology Press, Shanghai, 1987, p.137.